

A Collection of Integer Solutions to Non-homogeneous Ternary Nonic Diophantine Equation

$$3(x^2 + y^2) - 5xy = (k^2 + 11)z^9$$

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Abstract

This paper aims at determining non-zero distinct integer solutions to non-homogeneous ternary nonic Diophantine equation $3(x^2 + y^2) - 5xy = (k^2 + 11)z^9$. Transformation techniques and factorization methods are utilized to obtain the same. We are able to solve the higher degree equation through the methods suggested above for obtaining plenty of non-zero distinct integer solutions.

Keywords: Ternary nonic equation, Non-homogeneous nonic equation, Integer solutions, Transformation technique, Factorization method

Introduction

The theory of Diophantine equations is an ancient subject that typically involves solving, polynomial equation in two or more variables or a system of polynomial equations with the number of unknowns greater than the number of equations, in integers and occupies a pivotal role in the region of mathematics. The subject of Diophantine equations has fascinated and inspired both amateurs and mathematicians alike and so they merit special recognition. Solving higher degree Diophantine equations can be challenging as they involve finding integer solutions that satisfy the given polynomial equation. Learning about the various techniques to solve these higher power Diophantine equation in successfully deriving their solutions help us understand how numbers work and their significance in different areas of mathematics and science. For the sake of clear understanding by the readers, one may refer the varieties of Cubic, Quintic, Sextic and Heptic Diophantine equations with multi variables [1-37]. This paper aims at determining

many integer solutions to non-homogeneous polynomial equation of degree nine with three unknowns given by $3(x^2 + y^2) - 5xy = (k^2 + 11)z^9$.

Method of analysis

The non-homogeneous ternary nonic Diophantine equation to be solved is

$$3(x^2 + y^2) - 5xy = (k^2 + 11)z^9 \tag{1}$$

The insertion of the linear transformations

$$x = u + v, y = u - v, u \neq v \neq 0 \tag{2}$$

in (1) leads to the equation

$$u^2 + 11v^2 = (k^2 + 11)z^9 \tag{3}$$

Pattern 1

To start with, the choice

$$u = kv, k \neq 1 \tag{4}$$

in (3) gives

$$v^2 = z^9$$

which is satisfied by

$$v = s^{9t}, z = s^{2t}, s \neq 1$$

From (4), we have

$$u = ks^{9t}$$

In view of (2), one has

$$x = (k+1)s^{9t}, y = (k-1)s^{9t}$$

Thus, when $k \neq \pm 1$, the above values of x, y, z represent the non-zero distinct integer solutions to (1).

Pattern 2

After performing a few calculations, it is observed that (3) is satisfied by

$$\begin{aligned} u &= p(p^2 + 11q^2)^4(k^2 + 11)^5 \\ v &= q(p^2 + 11q^2)^4(k^2 + 11)^5 \\ z &= (p^2 + 11q^2)(k^2 + 11) \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

In view of (2) , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (p+q) (p^2 + 11q^2)^4 (k^2 + 11)^5 \\ y &= (p-q)(p^2 + 11q^2)^4 (k^2 + 11)^5 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Thus ,when $p \neq \pm q$, the values of x, y, z given by (5) & (6) represent non-zero distinct integer solutions to (1).

Pattern 3

Let

$$z = a^2 + 11b^2 = (a + i\sqrt{11}b) (a - i\sqrt{11}b) \tag{7}$$

Write

$$\begin{aligned} k^2 + 11 &= (k + i\sqrt{11}) (k - i\sqrt{11}) \\ u^2 + 11v^2 &= (u + i\sqrt{11}v) (u - i\sqrt{11}v) \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Substituting (7) & (8) in (3) and equating the positive factors , we have

$$\begin{aligned} (u + i\sqrt{11}v) &= (k + i\sqrt{11}) (a + i\sqrt{11}b)^9 \\ &= (k + i\sqrt{11}) [f(a,b) + i\sqrt{11}g(a,b)] \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f(a,b) &= a^9 - 11 \cdot 36 a^7 b^2 + 11^2 \cdot 126 a^5 b^4 - 11^3 \cdot 84 a^3 b^6 + 11^4 \cdot 9 a b^8 \\ g(a,b) &= 9 a^8 b - 11 \cdot 84 a^6 b^3 + 11^2 \cdot 126 a^4 b^5 - 11^3 \cdot 36 a^2 b^7 + 11^4 b^9 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

On equating the coefficients of corresponding terms ,we get

$$\begin{aligned} u &= kf(a,b) - 11g(a,b) \\ v &= f(a,b) + kg(a,b) \end{aligned}$$

In view of (2) , one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (k+1) f(a,b) + (k-11)g(a,b) \\ y &= (k-1) f(a,b) - (k+11)g(a,b) \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Thus , (7) & (11) satisfy (1).

Pattern 4

Rewrite (3) as

$$u^2 + 11v^2 = (k^2 + 11) z^9 * 1 \tag{12}$$

Assume the integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (12) as

$$1 = \frac{(p(s) + i\sqrt{11}q(s))(p(s) - i\sqrt{11}q(s))}{(r(s))^2} \tag{13}$$

where

$$p(s) = (2s^2 - 2s - 5), q(s) = (2s - 1), r(s) = (2s^2 - 2s + 6)$$

Substituting (7), (8) & (13) in (12) and equating the positive factors, we have

$$\begin{aligned} (u + i\sqrt{11}v) &= (k + i\sqrt{11})(f(a, b) + i\sqrt{11}g(a, b)) \frac{(p(s) + i\sqrt{11}q(s))}{r(s)} \\ &= [F(k, s) + i\sqrt{11}G(k, s)] \frac{(f(a, b) + i\sqrt{11}g(a, b))}{r(s)} \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F(k, s) &= (k p(s) - 11q(s)) \\ G(k, s) &= (p(s) + k q(s)) \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

On comparing the coefficients of corresponding terms in (14), one has

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \frac{[F(k, s)f(a, b) - 11G(k, s)g(a, b)]}{r(s)} \\ v &= \frac{[G(k, s)f(a, b) + F(k, s)g(a, b)]}{r(s)} \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

As our aim is to obtain integer solutions, replacing a by $r(s)A$ and b by $r(s)B$ in (7)

and (16), we have

$$z = (r(s))^2 (A^2 + 11B^2) \tag{17}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} u &= (r(s))^8 [F(k, s)f(A, B) - 11G(k, s)g(A, B)] \\ v &= (r(s))^8 [G(k, s)f(A, B) + F(k, s)g(A, B)] \end{aligned}$$

In view of (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (r(s))^8 \{f(A, B)[F(k, s) + G(k, s)] + g(A, B)[F(k, s) - 11G(k, s)]\} \\ y &= (r(s))^8 \{f(A, B)[F(k, s) - G(k, s)] - g(A, B)[F(k, s) + 11G(k, s)]\} \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Thus , (17) & (18) satisfy (1).

Note 1

Apart from (13) , one may have the following representations for the integer 1 :

$$(i) \quad 1 = \frac{(11r^2 - s^2 + i\sqrt{11}(2rs))(11r^2 - s^2 - i\sqrt{11}(2rs))}{(11r^2 + s^2)^2}$$

$$(ii) \quad 1 = \frac{(r^2 - 11s^2 + i\sqrt{11}(2rs))(r^2 - 11s^2 - i\sqrt{11}(2rs))}{(r^2 + 11s^2)^2}$$

$$(iii) \quad 1 = \frac{(p(s) + i\sqrt{11}q(s))(p(s) - i\sqrt{11}q(s))}{(r(s))^2}$$

where

$$p(s) = (22s^2 - 22s + 5) , q(s) = (2s - 1), r(s) = (22s^2 - 22s + 6)$$

Pattern 5

Taking

$$v = z^4 \tag{19}$$

in (3) , we have

$$u^2 = z^8 [(k^2 + 11)z - 11] \tag{20}$$

After some algebra , it is seen that (20) is satisfied by the values of z & v given by

$$\begin{aligned} z_n &= 1 + 2nk + (k^2 + 11)n^2 \\ u_n &= (1 + 2nk + (k^2 + 11)n^2)^4 [k + (k^2 + 11)n] \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

From (19), one has

$$v_n = (1 + 2nk + (k^2 + 11)n^2)^4$$

In view of (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x_n &= (1 + 2nk + (k^2 + 11)n^2)^4 [k + 1 + (k^2 + 11)n] \\ y_n &= (1 + 2nk + (k^2 + 11)n^2)^4 [k - 1 + (k^2 + 11)n] \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Thus, the values of x ,y, z given by (21) & (22) satisfy (1).

Conclusion

Solving the higher degree Diophantine equation and finding the non-zero distinct integer solutions are used in various fields like cryptography, Number patterns. The concepts of

Diophantine equations are encouraging the young researchers to discover new ideas in various fields like some mentioned above. To conclude, one may search for different types of higher degree Diophantine equations and their solutions.

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